

OPTMIZATION AND THERMAL CONDUCTION MODELING FOR A HYBRID REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIAL FOR SOLID ROCKET MOTOR INSULATION

A. F., Ahmed, and S. V. Hoa

Concordia Center for Composites, Department of Mechanical and industrial Engineering,
Center for Research on Polymers and Composites (CREPEC)

Concordia University

1455 de Maisonneuve Blvd. West, H3G 1M8

Montreal, Quebec, Canada

ashraf197275@yahoo.com, hoasuon@alcor.concordia.ca

SUMMARY

Optimization of reinforced elastomers for use as rocket motor insulators was done. Predictions of thermal conduction of these materials were done using different models and compared with measured values. Transient dynamic analysis is used to determine the response of these materials under a time-varying thermal load.

Keywords: solid rocket motor insulator, thermal conduction prediction, transient dynamic analysis

NOMENCLATURE

EPDM	Ethylene Propylene Diene Monomer
AP	Ammonium Polyphosphate
CCF	Chopped Carbon Fiber
PCA	Peroxide Cross linking Agent
KP	Kevlar Pulp
Phr	Part per hundred ratios
DSC	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
TGA	Thermo Gravimetric Analysis
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy

1- INTRODUCTION

Internal insulation in a solid rocket motor is a layer of heat-barrier material placed between the internal surface of the case and the propellant. The primary function of internal insulation is to prevent the rocket motor case from reaching temperatures that may endanger its structural integrity. The insulation material should be light, pliable, non toxic, thermal resistant, ablative resistant and stable up to 2760 °C (5000 °F) [1]. The currently used insulators have deficiency in at least one of the primary requirements. The first aim of

the research is to provide an understanding of the mechanism, the principle, and the process for making polymeric thermal insulants. The second aim is to produce thermal insulants based on polymers with different fillers having different compositions. These show improvement over current used insulators.

2- OPTIMIZATION

Optimization of developed hybrid reinforced rubbers for use as rocket motor insulators was presented [1]. Such insulation is based on chopped carbon fiber and aramid fiber in pulp form (Kevlar pulp) as reinforcement for Ethylene Propylene Diene Monomer (EPDM). Optimization of the relative amounts of chopped carbon fibers and Kevlar pulp inside EPDM by mixing and curing different compositions is shown in Table (1). Physical, mechanical (density, hardness, tensile strength and elongation), thermal (effective thermal conductivity, effective specific heat capacity and effective thermal diffusivity) and ablative properties of different compositions were measured. Thermo-gravimetric analyses versus relative hybrid reinforcement content, as well as differential scanning calorimetric results were obtained. The effect of changing the relative amounts of chopped carbon fiber and Kevlar pulp volume fractions was studied. As a result the best parameters of the selected materials (Ethylene Propylene Diene Monomer, chopped carbon fiber and Kevlar pulp) which give the maximum performance were obtained.

Table 1: Material samples compositions

Sample No	EPDM phr	AP phr	CCF phr	KP phr	PCA phr
(20)	100	60	5	45	6
(21)	100	60	10	40	6
(22)	100	60	15	35	6
(23)	100	60	20	30	6
(24)	100	60	30	20	6
(25)	100	60	35	15	6
(26)	100	60	40	10	6
(27)	100	60	45	5	6

CCF is generally used for reinforcement in thermoplastic molding compounds requiring high strength and modulus, low density, electrical conductivity, dimensional stability, low thermal expansion and excellent friction/wear properties. They do not melt or soften with heat, allowing them to be used in such high temperature applications. In fact, their strength actually increases with temperature in non-oxidizing atmospheres. These unique properties are the result of the fiber microstructure, in both the axial and transverse directions. KP is an organic and highly fibrillated form of fiber in the aromatic polyamide family which can be dispersed in different matrix. It has a unique combination of high strength, high modulus, toughness and thermal stability. The formulations were mixed using a C.W. Bra

bender mixer equipped with two sigma blades to attain uniform dispersion of the reinforcement inside EPDM. The formulations were cured using PCA under a press ($T = 170\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P = 28\text{ tons}$) using compression molding. Sheets with dimensions (300 x 150 x 3 mm, 300 x 150 x 1 mm) were made. 8 samples were mixed, cured and tested.

2.1 Testing

ASTM cutting die was used to cut samples from the cured sheet of the insulation. Instron tensometer and laser extensometer were used for the determination of the tensile strength and elongation. Shore A hardness was measured. The determination of Density of solid rubber sheets was done by using the rule of mixture. The nanoflash technique is used for the determination of the thermal diffusivity. Using this method, the front side of a plane-parallel to sample with a well defined thickness is heated by a short light or laser pulse. The resulting temperature rise on the back surface is measured versus time using an infrared detector. DSC is used to get the specific heat capacity for insulation composition. TGA analysis was used to establish the decomposition temperatures of the material composition. The formula $K = \rho \cdot A \cdot C_p$ is used to determine the thermal conductivity of the material.

2.2 Results and Discussion

Fig (1) shows tensile strength and elongation values. Increasing phr content of KP over 30 in EPDM inside the hybrid (decreasing CCF phr content) ($\text{CCF} + \text{KP} = 50$) will decrease the tensile strength of the material. This is due to the very high surface area of KP ($7\text{-}10\text{ m}^2/\text{gm}$). When the content of kp is over 30 phr, not all the fibers are wetted by the matrix during the mixing resulting in the decrease in tensile strength. The elongation increases with increasing the CCF phr content inside the hybrid (decreasing KP phr content).

Hardness values versus sample compositions are shown in Fig (2). Hardness increases with increasing KP content inside the hybrid (decreasing CCF phr content) ($\text{CCF} + \text{KP} = 50$).

Density values versus sample compositions are shown in Fig (2). Density increases by increasing CCF content inside the hybrid (decreasing KP phr content) ($\text{CCF} + \text{KP} = 50$). This is because of the higher density of CCF (1.81 g/cm^3) compared to EPDM (0.86 g/cm^3) and KP (1.44 g/cm^3).

Thermal diffusivities for the insulation compositions with different CCF + KP phr content at $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are also shown in Fig (3). Specific heat capacities for the different material compositions at $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are shown in Fig (3). It appears that increasing CCF content inside the hybrid (decreasing KP phr content) ($\text{CCF} + \text{KP} = 50$) in the material will result in decreasing the specific heat capacity of the material. This is due to the lower specific heat capacity of CCF (660 J/kg.C) as compared to KP (1450 J/kg.C) (reinforcement) and EPDM (the matrix) (2177 J/kg.C).

Thermal conductivities for the CCF + KP based compositions at $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are shown in Fig (4).

Fig (1) Tensile Strength & Elongation as a function of CCF + KP phr content

Fig (2) Hardness & Density for CCF + KP based samples

It appears that increasing CCF content inside the hybrid (decreasing KP phr content) (CCF + KP = 50) in the material will result in increasing the thermal conductivity of the material. This is due to the higher thermal conductivity of CCF (6.4 W/m.K) as compared to KP (0.04 W/m.K) and EPDM (0.36 W/m.K).

The resultant TGA curves which relate the weight % for every insulation composition sample with temperature for 5 phr CCF + 45 phr KP and 45 phr CCF + 5 phr KP based samples are shown in Fig (5) and Fig (6) respectively.

The TGA tests indicate for all compositions that an initial decomposition temperature for EPDM (matrix) occurs around 411 °C and the final decomposition is at 549 °C where EPDM decomposes to carbonaceous residue of free carbon. These provide a net effect of strong carbon based char which is highly erosion resistant. Also the tests indicate that an

initial decomposition temperature for ammonium polyphosphate (flame retardant agent) occurs around 577 °C and the final decomposition is at 725 °C.

Fig (3) Thermal diffusivity and specific heat capacity of the material as a function of CCF + KP phr content

Fig (4) Thermal conductivity as a function of CCF + KP phr content

The only stable ingredients above 1000 °C is CCF and KP which are stable up to 3445°C and 1450°C respectively, in addition to the carbon based char remains from decomposition of EPDM.

So CCF content increases inside the hybrid (decreasing KP phr content) (CCF + KP = 50) inside EPDM will result in the insulation efficiency increases with respect to decomposition. This is clear where the remaining weight for sample 20 (5 phr CCF + 45 phr KP based insulation) just before 1000 °C is 15 % of the total insulation weight as shown in Fig (5) while for sample (27) (45 phr CCF + 5 phr KP based insulation)

insulation composition is 36 % of the total insulation weight as shown in Fig (6). This is because CCF is more stable than KP with respect to decomposition.

Fig (5) TGA, DTGA curves for 5 CCF + 45 KP based insulation

Fig (6) TGA, DTGA curves for 45 CCF + 5 KP based insulation

As a conclusion, it appears that as CCF content increases [inside the hybrid (decreasing KP phr content) (CCF + KP = 50)] inside EPDM there will be improvement in the performance of EPDM with respect to decomposition and ablation resistance. At the same time, increasing CCF content reduces the performance of EPDM as solid rocket motor insulation with respect to thermal (thermal diffusivity and specific heat capacity) and mechanical properties.

3- THERMAL CONDUCTION MODELING

The predictions of thermal conduction of multiphase thermal insulation composite materials were done using series, parallel, Maxwell Eucken and effective medium theory models. Comparison with the measured values allows determining which model estimates best the thermal conductivity of composite insulation material [2].

The physical structures assumed in the derivations of the Series and Parallel models consist of layers of the components aligned either perpendicular or parallel to the heat flow, as indicated in Fig (7) (a), (b) respectively. The Maxwell–Eucken model assumes a dispersion of small spheres within a continuous matrix of a different component, with the spheres being far enough apart such that the local distortions to the temperature distributions around each of the spheres do not interfere with their neighbors' temperature distributions as shown in Fig (7) (c). The EMT model assumes a completely random distribution of all the components as shown in Fig (7) (d).

Series, Parallel, Maxwell–Eucken and Effective Medium Theory models are shown in formulas (1), (2), (3) and (4) respectively.

$$K = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{v_i}{k_i}} \quad (1)$$

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^m k_i v_i \quad (2)$$

$$K = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m k_i v_i \frac{3k_1}{2k_1 + k_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^m v_i \frac{3k_1}{2k_1 + k_i}} \quad (3)$$

$$K = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m k_i v_i \frac{3K}{2K + k_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^m v_i \frac{3K}{2K + k_i}} \quad (4)$$

Where

- k_i thermal conductivity of a component ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{C}^{-1}$)
- K effective thermal conductivity of the material ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{C}^{-1}$)
- m number of components inside composite material
- v_i volume fraction of a component i

Formulas (1), (2), (3) and (4) are used to calculate the effective thermal conductivity for the rocket motor insulation compositions in Table (1). The results are compared with experimental values.

Fig (8) shows the difference between the calculated values using parallel, series, effective medium theory and the Maxwell–Eucken models with the measured values for the thermal conductivities of a hybrid of CCF and KP (total reinforcement 50 phr) (unequal volume fraction of CCF and KP inside the hybrid) based insulants.

Fig (7) Models based on the structure of the homogenous phase and dispersed phase

Series model

(a)

Parallel model

(b)

Maxwell–Eucken 1

(c)

EMT model

(d)

The model that gives results closest to the experimental measurements for CCF + KP (unequal amounts) based compositions is the series model which assumes layers of the components aligned perpendicular to the heat flow. The difference is within 16.9 % of the measured values.

As a result the thermal conductivity of CCF + KP (unequal amounts) reinforced EPDM can be estimated by the formula:

$$K = 1.169 \frac{1}{(v_{CCF} / k_{CCF}) + (v_{KP} / k_{KP}) + (v_{EPDM} / k_{EPDM})} \quad (5)$$

with an accuracy $\pm 1.4 \%$.

Fig (8) Calculated and measured thermal conductivities as function of CCF + KP phr content (unequal phr of CCF and KP) (total reinforcement 50 phr)

TRANSIENT DYNAMIC ANALYSIS

Transient dynamic analysis is used to determine the dynamic response of multiphase thermal insulation composite materials under a time-varying thermal load [3]. The numerical solution is done by using Matlab PDE tool.

The general one dimensional heat equation that applies is:

$$d \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (c \nabla u) + au = f$$

For this dimensional heat equation with no internal heat generation, assuming a triangular mesh on Ω and $t \geq 0$, expands the solution to the PDE (as a function of x) in the Finite Element Method basis:

$$u(x, t) = \sum_i U_i(t) \phi_j(x)$$

Substituting the expansion into the PDE, multiplying with a test function Φ_j , integrating over Ω , and applying Green's formula and the boundary conditions yields the solution. Modeling the ablation test appears to be a simple one dimensional heat equation where there is heat conduction through the thickness. There are two aspects which make this model more complicated. The first aspect is the reduction of the material thickness with time and the second one is the variation of material properties with time. The model was done by taking into consideration both the reduction in the thickness and variation of material properties with time.

The model was done by considering a sample of the insulation material with known properties (based on CCF + KP reinforcement) with 3 mm thickness and width 20 cm. The sample is bonded to a steel piece with the same dimensions. Assuming perfect contact between the insulation material and the steel piece with known properties and the temperature at the top surface of the insulation material is the same temperature of the torch used (2010° C). The bottom surface of steel is subjected to convection heat transfer by air with coefficient of heat convection 10 W/m².K as shown in Fig (9).

Fig (9) Ablation geometric model (1 layer), at t = 0 second

At reaction temperature, endothermic chemical decomposition occurs, the organic matrix pyrolyzes into carbonized material and gaseous products. The char layer formed after decomposition reduces the heat flux passing through it. This blocking action can reduce the net heating of the ablative material by more than 50%. The heat flow rate through the thickness x is

$$q = - KA \frac{dT}{dx}$$

Since the area A is constant, the only way to reduce the heat flow rate through the thickness is to reduce the thermal conductivity of the material by 50 % since we need to find the temperature gradient through the thickness (dT/dx).

Solving the problem for 60 seconds of total time and with increment of 0.01 second for any 4 sub steps of time (for example from 0 to 1, 1 to 10, 10 to 30 and 30-60 seconds). The temperature distribution as a function of thickness at different times is shown in Fig (10).

Fig (10) Temperature distribution as a function of thickness at different times for 1 layer (CCF + KP) based insulation

CONCLUSION

Reinforcement of EPDM with CCF + KP improves the performance of the material as application for solid rocket motor insulation with respect to mechanical properties, thermal properties, ablation resistance and decomposition resistance. The best volume fraction which gives the best performance of the insulation material is 25 phr CCF + 25 phr KP. The best model to estimate the thermal conductivity of CCF + KP based composite insulation material is the series model which assumes layers of the components aligned perpendicular to the heat flow. An ablation model for these materials was done to estimate the case temperatures under a time-varying thermal load.

References

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